

Probabilistic Semantic Mapping for Vision-Based Systems: Integrating Perception and Uncertainty

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Abstract—This study presents a system implemented on a quadruped robot, designed to generate a multi-layered map that incorporates semantic information and uncertainty, specifically tailored for Search & Rescue robotics. The article details the development of a machine learning model based on visual data for recognizing people and environmental features and its integration into an architecture for mapping and navigation. Extensive testing of the system in two different locations, conducted using Boston Dynamics’ Spot robot with an external ZED2 depth camera, is also described.

Index Terms—semantic map, vision-based, quadruped robots

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, quadruped robots have been used for several applications, primarily for inspecting areas that may pose health hazards for human operators. Quadruped robots are well known for their mobility, which allows them to navigate hazardous terrains and carry loads, distinguishing them from drones. Due to this ability, quadruped robots are becoming integral in Search and Rescue (SAR) operations. By deploying SAR robots in inspection missions immediately after a disaster occurs, rescuers can arrive at the scene with relevant information gathered by robots, thus improving their Situational Awareness, [1]. Greater situational awareness helps first responders plan their missions more accurately and safely.

It is important to understand the needs of rescuers and determine which information is most crucial to gather during a search and rescue mission. In our previous work [2], we conducted an interview with first responders to collect insight into their needs and the initial information that should be gathered when a disaster occurs. They envisioned a fully autonomous robot exploring the environment and recording data that could be analyzed outside the building.

Our system can create a map tailored for SAR scenarios, which can locate People, Doors, Cracks, and Stairs in the environment. During the interview with first responders, they emphasized that collecting the number and location of people in the environment is crucial for planning a path inside the building to help them exit safely, as well as for determining the number of ambulances needed. Identifying the location of

doors is particularly valuable for planning safe paths to areas the robot cannot explore. The location of stairs is important for improving the robot’s ability to climb and explore other floors of the building. Regarding cracks in the walls, knowing their precise location can help assess the structural stability of the building, as a crack in a load-bearing wall requires different procedures than one in a partition wall.

II. METHODOLOGY

We aim to develop a system capable of recognizing and localizing relevant features in the environment during the robot’s movement. Semantic maps integrate information about an object’s significance within the environment [3]. These maps are used to improve the reliability of navigation algorithms by embedding information about the object’s meaning, such as its average height. Our goal is to provide first responders with a semantic map that allows them to easily retrieve the location and number of relevant detected features in the environment. We aim to develop a hardware-independent, highly modular solution that can be applied to more general scenarios.

We chose to detect the following features using a vision-based system: People, Doors, Stairs, and Cracks. We created a dataset on RoboFlow¹. Before training, we performed several augmentation steps to ensure robust detections. We then trained a YOLOv5-based model for 100 epochs with a batch size of 64, without freezing any layers. We trained three different YOLOv5-based models before deciding to use the YOLOv5n, to ensure a fast system, running at a fixed frequency of 2Hz. The model’s precision on the test set is 0.609, while the recall is 0.499. Although performance can be improved, we consider it sufficient to proceed to the next phase, which involves integrating the vision system with the mapping one. The model is integrated into the computer vision computational unit, and the detections include the class, the confidence score, and the position relative to the camera frame.

The navigation unit, which builds the map of the environment using a SLAM algorithm, receives the detection and transforms the coordinates from the camera frame. To integrate these detections with the geometric information, it is important

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¹The dataset is publicly available at <https://universe.roboflow.com/stair-eyhvv/rex-cue-2>

to account for the detection confidence. We drew inspiration from Probabilistic Occupancy Grid Algorithms [4] to generate a multi-layered map. Each layer \mathcal{M}^L holds information about one feature of the map: (1) stores data on obstacles, while (2) through (5) represent the locations of relevant detected features. Layers (2) through (5) have a resolution of $0.5m$, and each cell holds a value between 0 and 100, representing the confidence that the cell is occupied by the corresponding feature. The cells are updated as explained in Algorithm 1.

Please notice, one detection marks 9 cells, corresponding to an area of approximately $2.25m^2$. This helps increase the confidence in cells that are closer together, as two nearby detection areas may merge. Similar to how the Probabilistic Occupancy Grid map works, if no detection is within the sensor’s field of view, the area should be cleared of previous detections. We approximate the camera’s field of view and decrease the value of the cells in that area at a frequency of $0.5Hz$. The clearing frequency is implemented slower than the marking frequency, as it is more critical to avoid False Negatives than to have a few False Positive. A False Positive results in wasted time checking if the detection was valid, which is less relevant compared to the time saved by not having to verify all true negatives. However, a False Negative implies a missed feature.

Algorithm 1 Map Update algorithm

Require: N detections $\mathcal{O} = \{\mathcal{M}^{o_1}, \dots, \mathcal{M}^{o_n}\}$, a map layer $\mathcal{M}^L = \{map_{1,1}, \dots, map_{maxX,maxY}\}$

for all $\mathcal{M}^{o_i} \in \mathcal{O}$ **do**

$\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \emptyset$

$(x, y) \leftarrow getMapCell(\mathcal{M}^{o_i})$

$\mathcal{C} \leftarrow (x, y)$

$\mathcal{C} \leftarrow \mathcal{C} \cup 8_neighbours(x, y)$

for all $(j, k) \in \mathcal{C}$ **do**

if $(j, k) = (x, y)$ **then**

$value \leftarrow confidence(\mathcal{M}^{o_i})$

else $value \leftarrow 0.5confidence(\mathcal{M}^{o_i})$

end if

$Prob = 0.5value + 0.5$

$LogOdd \leftarrow \log(\frac{Prob}{1-Prob}) + \log(\frac{map_{j,k}}{1-map_{j,k}})$

$map_{j,k} \leftarrow 100 \frac{e^{LogOdd}}{1+e^{LogOdd}}$

end for

end for

To test our system we used the Spot robot from Boston Dynamics, with the Spot Core as the navigation unit and the ZED2 camera by Stereolabs paired with the NVIDIA Jetson Nano as the computer vision unit. We tested our system at two locations. The first location, on the second floor of the E Building of the DIBRIS Department at the University of Genova, located at Via Opera Pia 13 in Genova, features 20 doors, two staircases one ascending and one descending, and 2 people present. The second location is the ground floor of Villa Bonino, headquarters of DIBRIS, located at Viale Causa 13, also in Genova. This location has 9 doors, 3 staircases

(one leading downstairs and two upstairs), and 2 people. Since Cracks were not present in either location, we decided not to evaluate the system’s performance for that class.

At each location, we asked 5 people to teleoperate the robot along a predefined path 5 times. In each run, the experimenter changed the location of people in the environment, their posture (sitting, laying down, standing), and the status (open or closed) of doors. In Figure 1, the Obstacle Layer and the People layer, in yellow, are shown. For each experimental run, we calculated the number of True Positives, False Positives, and False Negatives, in addition to the IoU. To compute these metrics, we set a threshold $th \in \{20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80\}$ and we removed detections with confidence below each threshold. With a threshold $th = 50$ at the second location, we obtained a precision of 0.787 for the Doors class, 0.691 for the People class, and 0.592 for the Stairs class. We observed that the model’s performance varies significantly depending on the class being detected, likely due to challenges inherent to the location, such as narrow, dark staircases leading down or difficult configurations of people in the environment.

Fig. 1. Obstacles (black) and Person instances (yellow) at the second location.

III. CONCLUSION

We developed a system that integrates semantic information, extracted from a YOLO-based model, into the layers of a semantic map while accounting for detection uncertainties. The system addresses the specific challenges of Search and Rescue scenarios. Testing was conducted with Boston Dynamics’ Spot robot across multiple locations, and we evaluated its detection performance. The system successfully identifies most instances of persons, doors, and stairs, though it occasionally produces false positives. Future work will focus on improving the model’s robustness in scenarios where individuals are lying down or obscured by debris. We also plan to evaluate performance in environments with cracked walls and test the system with integrated autonomous exploration.

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